

TYPES OF MEMORY AND ITS PROCESSES

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Abstract: This article provides extensive information about the types of memory and its processes, as well as the psychology of memory, clear and smooth ways to improve it.

Key words: memory, action memory, emotional memory, long term memory, psychology of memory.

Memory is a continuation of our past. It is the most durable of our abilities. Memory is at the core of human abilities and is a prerequisite for learning, acquiring knowledge and developing skills. Neither a person nor society can function normally without memory. Thanks to his memory and his improvement, man was separated from the animal world and reached his current peak. It is impossible to imagine the further development of mankind without the constant improvement of this function. Memory allows us to collect impressions of the world around us and serves as a basis for acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities. Only memory helps to preserve the culture of humanity, the application of our thinking and the passage of our feelings. Without your images of the external world that appear in the cortex of the brain, it will not disappear. They leave a mark that remains for a long time. Memory in our psyche serves as their reserve. All processes that take place in it are called mnemonic processes (from the Greek "mnema" - memory). Thus, memory is the mental process of remembering, storing, and later recalling past experiences by a person. The place of memory in human life is incomparable. Without memory, a person would remain "in a state of eternal infancy" (I.M. Sechenov). S.L. Rubinstein said: "Without memory, we would be creatures of the moment. Our past would be dead for the future. According to the past, badar would disappear in the past.

The peculiarity of memory as a mental process is that it is not aimed at direct reflection of the surrounding world, does not deal with material objects and events. Reflection of the world of bodies is carried out in perception and thinking. Memory deals with the "second reflection" of received images and concepts. Every cognitive process becomes a continuous memory, and every memory becomes something else. Each mental process serves as a condition for the implementation of another process (or the next stage of that process). This means that it becomes a "secondary" product,

has the ability to be realized in the imagination, and can serve as a basis for the further development of the process.

Another characteristic of memory is that it is directed in one direction: from the past to the future. The main working mechanism of human memory is its future orientation. The main task of memory is to serve the future. Reflecting on the past is seen as a means of achieving results in the future.

There are groups of physical, chemical, biochemical, physiological, information-cybernetic theories, as well as psychological theories related to memory. Among such theories, we will consider psychological theories that are useful in understanding the laws of memory activity and developing methods of its management.

One of the first psychological theories of memory is the associative theory, which arose in the 17th century and was first developed in England and Germany in the 18th and 19th centuries. This theory is based on V osnoe dannoy teorii lejit ponyatie association - the concept of connection between separate unique phenomena of the psyche developed by G. Ebbinghaus, G. Müller, A. Pilscher and others. According to this theory, memory is understood as a complex system of short-term and long-term associations that are stable in terms of similarity, temporal and spatial proximity. According to this theory, many laws were discovered, in particular, the law of forgetting by G. Ebbinghaus. During the first hour, up to 60% of the information received is forgotten, and after six days, less than 20% of the text memorized for the first time is retained. Over time, the associative theory encountered a number of problems that needed to be solved, the main of which was to explain the selective nature of human memory.

In modern psychology, a theory that studies the activity of a person as a connecting factor of all his mental processes, as well as the formation of memory processes, is recognized as the main concept. Based on this concept, the process of memorization, storage and recall is determined by the place of information in the activity of the object.

Memory consists of the following main processes: remembering, remembering and forgetting.

The classification of memory types according to the nature of mental activity was first introduced by P.P. Suggested by Blonsky. Types of activity may be dominated by motor, emotional, sensory, mental types of mental activity. Each of these activities is expressed in actions and their products, feelings, images, and thoughts. Blonsky was able to identify the differences between certain types of memory.

We present the characteristics of these four types of memory.

Action memory is the ability to remember, store, and recall various actions or systems. It serves as a basis for the formation of various movement skills and skills, for example, walking, driving a car, dancing, etc.

Emotional memory is the memory of experienced sensations and emotional states. Emotions always tell us how our needs and interests are being satisfied, how our relationship with the environment is being implemented. The sensations experienced and stored in the memory are manifested as messages that initiate action or prevent action that provoked negative experiences in the past.

Pictorial memory is a memory related to images, scenes of nature and life, as well as sounds, smells, tastes. It is related to sight, hearing, touch, smell and taste. Sometimes eidetic memory is found in some individuals (eidetics) who have the ability to remember and recall previously perceived bodies and scenes very vividly and vividly. Eidetic images appear in the absence of a body and are similar to imagination in that they have the characteristic of consistent visuality, which is not characteristic of ordinary imagination.

Long-term memory is one of the types of memory that has the ability to retain material for an unlimited period of time and information in an unlimited amount.

Working memory is a type of memory necessary for the performance of the current activity, which manifests itself in the performance of certain activities, serves this activity according to the storage of information coming from short-term and long-term memory. This type of memory occupies an intermediate state between short-term and long-term memories, depending on the duration of information storage and its properties. The storage time of the material in the operating memory is determined by the duration of the operation.

The psychology of memory offers clear and smooth ways to improve it. Among them: long-term memory; active repetition, organization of useful, vivid, figurative associative connections, memory exercises; referring to a specific situation and mood; retelling the memories before they are lost through false news; to prevent confusion of information; is self-monitoring and repetition.

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